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Effect of Supplementation Frequency on Cattle Intake and Performance Grazing a Deferred Tropical Pasture

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Tropical grasses utilization in semiarid environments during winter can limit cattle intake because of forage quality and availability. In this case, cattle supplementation with energetic and proteins concentrates, is a viable practice in order to improve forage intake, and thus the animal performance (Stobbs, 1973). Several studies have shown that infrequent protein supplementation decreases feeding cost achieving similar performance compared with every day supplementation (Farmer *et al* 2004). Even though infrequent protein supplementation has been widely studied, little research has been carried out with regards to discontinuous energy supplementation. Thus, this study evaluated the effect of winter supplementation frequency (continuous or discontinuous, based on energetic concentrate) on the dry matter intake (DMI) and average daily gain (ADG) of heifers grazing deferred pastures (*Chloris gayana*) in the Argentine Semiarid Chaco region. Braford heifers were subjected to two supplementation treatments based on corn (70%) and soybean expeller (30%): a) Daily supply (continuous) at 1.10% LW, b) Discontinuous supply (four times per week) at 1.92% LW – in order to reach an equal supplementation level in week basis, for two grazing periods (GP) of 21 days during the winter 2013 (Period 1[P1]: June; Period 2[P2]: August). Each treatment had two replicates with 7 animals, and the initial weight was 206.3 ± 10.4 for P1 and 233.3 ± 12.3 kg for P2. Fecal collection was made for 7 days of each period on selected animals grazing individual subplots. Diet digestibility was estimated using the acid detergent insoluble ash (ADIA) as internal marker. Simultaneously, initial and final forage availability and plant fractions (leaf, stem, and dead material) were measured above and below the grazing level. Pasture grazing layers were divided or classified in: upper (> 21 cm above the ground) and lower strata (< 21 cm). Forage digestibility and crude protein concentration (CP) was determined at each grazing strata. Deferred forage quality was different ($P < 0.01$) between grazing periods due to the pasture growth cessation and winter frosts occurrences. Chemical composition of forage had the following values: 74 – 64 g Kg⁻¹ CP, 330 – 347 g Kg⁻¹ NDF and 701 – 677 g Kg⁻¹ ADF for June (P1) and August (P2), respectively. Dry matter intake, *in vivo* DM digestibility and ADG did not differ between treatments (Table 1, $P < 0.05$), but they were different between grazing periods. The leaves fraction selection above the grazing layer showed higher correlation with CP. During the first GP, fractions used were stems from upper strata and leaves of both strata. Furthermore, during the second GP when forage was completely dry or dead, the heifers consumed leaves and small stem fractions of the upper grazing strata.

Table 1: Effect supplementation frequency on heifers DM intake (DMI; gBW⁻¹), *in vivo* DM digestibility (DMD; g/kgDM) and average daily gain (ADG; g/day) for two grazing periods.

GP	Continuous	Discontinuous	F	P Value
P1				
DMI,	22.10	25.11	2.56	0.13
DMD	660	670	0.58	0.46
ADG	762	704	0.69	0.41
P2				
DMI	21,60	19,38	2.29	0.15
DMD	610	600	0.44	0.83
ADG	626	613	0.08	0.85

Our results indicate that both supplementation systems, based on deferred *Chloris gayana* pastures allow to achieve similar animal performance, although the ADG and intake decrease as the dry season progresses and deferred forage quality decreases independently of treatments. Under this conditions pasture leaf availability may to be a good forage intake estimator.

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Stobbs, T.H (1973). *Aust. J. Agric. Res.* **24**, 809.

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